

Asymmetric Reductions. Part I. Reduction of Ketones with Active Isobornyloxyaluminium Dichloride*

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'A series of acyclic ketones has been reduced with active isobornyloxyaluminium dichloride, prepared from (-) isoborneol and mixed hydride to obtain partially active alcohols. The optical purity of the alcohols ranges from a minimum of 2.8% in case of methylethylcarbinol to a maximum of 25.9% in case of methylphenylcarbinol. The preponderant enantiomer in each case has the absolute R-configuration, predictable from the preferred transition state of the reaction. The method is simple and may be useful for the preparation of partially active alcohols.'

A number of methods are available in the literature¹ for the reduction of dissymmetric ketones of the type, RCOR' to partially active alcohols with various asymmetric reagents. The methods are all based on the principle that the reactions generally proceed through two diastereoisomeric transition states one of which is energetically more favoured than the other. The reactions are carried out under strictly kinetically controlled condition. It has been previously observed by us² that isobornyloxyaluminium dichloride (II) obtained by the action of isoborneol (I) on mixed hydride³ (a mixture of lithium aluminium hydride and anhydrous aluminium chloride in a molecular proportion of 1 : 3) is a very good reducing agent for conversion of ketones to alcohols. The reduction which is brought about by hydride transfer evidently through a quasi six-membered cyclic transition state similar to that in the Meerwein-Ponndorf reaction⁴, is virtually irreversible⁵ and subject to marked steric approach controls⁵. It was therefore hoped that the use of (-) isoborneol (I) in the reagent would lead to high asymmetric induction during reduction of ketones of the type, RCOR'. A similar reagent, namely, isobornyloxymagnesium bromide has already been used for asymmetric reduction of phenylloxalic acid⁶ and a few deuterated aldehydes⁷. This reagent is however less reactive and requires much longer time for completion thereby allowing the products to equilibrate to some extent (cf. ref. 2). Isobornyloxyaluminium dichloride, on the other hand, is a far more reactive reagent, the reduction being completed in most cases within 15 min. at room temperature or below. On this consideration, a number of acyclic ketones, mostly alkyl and aryl methyl ketones, have been reduced with the active reagent (II) and the optical purities of the resultant alcohols determined. The results are shown in Table I.

*For a preliminary account, see this *Journal*, 1967, 44, 165.

1. Eliel, *Stereochemistry of Carbon Compounds*, McGraw Hill Book Co. Inc. New York, 1962, p 68.
2. Eliel and Nasipuri, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1965, 30, 3809.
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5. Dauben, Fonken, and Noyace, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 78, 2579.
6. Vavon and Antonini, *Compt. rend.* 1951, 232, 1120.
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TABLE I

Entry	Alcohol ^a	Rotation observed ^b		Optical purity ^c %	Configuration
		$[\alpha]_D^{25-30}$	in degree		
1	EtCHOHMe	-0.192,	-0.385	1.0, 2.8	R
2	Bu ^t CHOHMe	-1.02,	-1.19	5.0, 5.7	R
3	Pr ⁱ CHOHMe	-0.62,	-0.875	11.6, 16.4	R
4	Bu ^t CHOHMe	-0.93,	-1.40	12.1, 18.1	R
5	PhCHOHMe	+8.52,	+11.04	20.0, 25.9	R
6	PhCH ₂ CHOHMe	0.0, 0.0		0.0, 0.0	—

^aAlcohols were regenerated from acid phthalates and rotations taken in neat liquid.

^bResults of two different experiments.

^cCalculated on maximum rotation recorded^b.

A mixture of (-)isoborneol (~90%) and (+)borneol (~10%), obtained from reduction of readily available (+) camphor with lithium aluminium hydride⁸ is used for the preparation of the reagent. The presence of small amount of (+)borneol does not affect the results in any way since the corresponding borneol-complex reacts so much more slowly⁹. The ketone and the reagent are taken in a molecular proportion of 1 : 1.3. Further excess of reagent does not much improve the optical yield. The reagent has been prepared by slowly adding an ethereal solution of isoborneol (I) to a cold solution of mixed hydride. The ketone is then dropped in gradually and the temperature is allowed to rise up to room temperature. In each case, the preponderant isomer of alcohol has the absolute R

(L and S stand for large and small groups respectively)

configuration¹⁰ (IV) in agreement with the theoretically preferred transition state (III), where the small group S and the bulky quaternary O₁-group of camphor are on the same side of the quasi six-membered ring. This arrangement will no doubt involve least steric interaction. The absolute configuration of (+)camphor and hence of (-)isoborneol, its reduction product is already known¹¹.

8. Heilbron and Bunbury, "Dictionary of Organic Compounds", London, 1953.

9. Noyce and Denny, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 5743.

10. Klyne, "Progress in Stereochemistry," Butterworths Scientific Publications, London, 1954, vol. 1., p.201

11. Birch, *Ann. Rep. Proc. Chem.*, 1950, 47, 192.

Contrary to our expectation that a reagent like (–)isborneol with three asymmetric centres should lead to high asymmetric induction, the optical yields in the present experiments are rather poor*. The maximum optical purity achieved is 25.9% in case of methylphenylcarbinol and the minimum 2.8% in case of methylethylcarbinol. As expected the stereospecificity in the reduction increases with the increase of branching in the α -carbon of the alkyl group of the ketones (see for example entries 1-4 in Table I). The method is very simple, the starting material easily available, and it may therefore be very useful for the preparation of partially active alcohols. Moreover, the configurations of the resultant alcohols are readily predictable. Recently, Cervinka¹³ has reduced a number of methyl alkyl and methyl aryl ketones with a mixture of lithium aluminium hydride and optically active aminoalcohols such as quinine and obtained partially active alcohols. The method has one serious disadvantage, namely, the absolute configurations of the alcohols are not often unambiguously determined since both steric and electronic factors are to be considered for preferred transition state.

The lower boiling alcohols such as the alkylmethylcarbinols are directly distilled from the reduction products and further purified through the formation of acid phthalates and regeneration. The yields of recovery vary from 15 to 30%. The main impurity is camphene arising out of decomposition of isborneol-complex and is completely removed by this procedure. The arylcarbinols are isolated by carefully controlled steam-distillation whereby the camphoraceous materials are all completely removed. The yield of recovery in these cases is much better ($\approx 50\%$). The purity of the alcohols is checked by their b.p.s and refractive indices.

Two cases of failure have been observed. Reduction of benzyl methyl ketone with the above reagent goes without any measurable asymmetric induction. *p*-Methoxyacetophenone forms a complex with anhydrous aluminium chloride which is insoluble in ether but soluble in tetrahydrofuran; but the ketone is not reduced at all by this reagent in either solvent.

Asymmetric reduction of a series of aryl alkyl ketones are in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials.—All the ketones were purified by distillation before use. *t*-Butyl methyl ketone was prepared according to the method described in Organic Synthesis¹². (+) Camphor was reduced with lithium aluminium hydride in ethereal solution to obtain a mixture of (–)isborneol and (+)borneol having $[\alpha]_D^{20} -24.7$ (α 5.6 in EtOH). Most of the reductions were carried out with this mixture. Pure (–)isborneol free from (+) borneol was prepared from the mixture by use of *o*-nitrobenzoyl chloride and steam-distillation¹⁴. Solution of lithium aluminium hydride in ether was standardised before use with iodine solution in benzene.

Asymmetric Reductions.—This reduction is described as typical of those summarised in table I. To an ice-cold stirred solution of anhydrous aluminium chloride (5.34 g., 0.04

*See however, Nasipuri and Sarkar, this *Journal*, 1967, 44, 165.

12. Cervinka, *Coll. Czech. Chem. Comm.*, 1965, 30, 1684.

13. Gilman and Blatt, "Organic Synthesis", John Wiley & Sons, New York, 1956, coll. vol. 1, p 462.

14. Jackman, Mackbeth and Mills, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 1717, 2641.

mole) in ether (50 ml.) was added 1M ethereal solution of lithium aluminium hydride (10 ml., 0.01mole) all at once. After 30 min., (-) isborneol (6.2 g., 0.04 mole) (or an equivalent mixture of isborneol and borneol obtained from camphor) in ether (30 ml.) was slowly added. The evolution of hydrogen was observed by means of an exit tube held under water, which was very brisk until towards the end when it ceased altogether. A slight excess of (-) isborneol was generally taken in order to avoid any unreacted hydride. The reaction vessel was then removed from the ice-bath and the mixture stirred for a few min. more. A solution of the ketone (0.03 mole) in ether (20 ml.) was then slowly introduced in the still cold solution of the reagent within 15 min., during which the mixture warmed up to room temperature. The stirring was continued for 30 min., more at this temperature to complete the reduction, the solution cooled, and decomposed by careful addition of 3N H_2SO_4 . The ethereal layer was separated, the aqueous solution extracted twice with alcohol-free ether, the combined extract once washed with a little water and dried over anhydrous K_2CO_3 overnight. The ether was removed by slow distillation through an efficient fractionating column and the residue worked up for isolation of the alcohol. An analysis of the reduction product of acetophenone by vapour phase chromatography on carbowax 20 M column showed major peaks of camphor, methylphenylcarbinol and minor peaks of camphene, isborneol and borneol but no peak corresponding to acetophenone. The methods of isolation of the desired alcohol from the mixture were construed depending on the b.p.s of the alcohols. Two procedures were generally adopted; they are as follows:

Method (a).—In case of the lower boiling alcohols, namely, the alkylmethylcarbinols, the residue after removal of ether was slowly distilled using a short fractionating column and the fractions corresponding to the boiling range of the respective alcohols were collected. The yields of these crude alcohols were almost theoretical. The major impurities in these fractions (b.p. 100—135°) was camphene which was dextrorotatory. To remove this, the alcohol was directly converted into acid phthalate by heating with phthalic anhydride either in presence of pyridine or in toluene solution. The phthalate was steam-distilled until completely freed from all camphoraceous substances and then hydrolysed with 30% aqueous alkali. The alcohol thus set free was taken up in ether, dried over anhydrous $MgSO_4$, and distilled using a good fractionating column. The recovery was usually 15-30%. The b.p.s and refractive indices agreed well with those recorded in the literature. The rotation was observed using a 1 dm. tube in sodium light. Duplicate experiments were performed in each case. The results are given in table I.

Method (b).—In case of the higher boiling alcohols, namely, the arylalkylcarbinols, the residue after evaporation of ether was mixed with water (500 ml.) and the mixture steam-distilled for some time. The hot aqueous mother liquor was filtered off from the floating solids and the filtrate kept aside. The steam-distillate which contained some semi-solid mass was again taken up in water (500 ml.) and submitted to further steam-distillation. The hot aqueous solution was filtered and the filtrate combined with the previous one. The process was once more repeated with the steam-distillate. The combined filtrate from the three operations was then taken into a 2L flask and a rapid current of steam passed through it until the solution did not smell of camphor. The solution was once more filtered, cooled in an ice-bath, and saturated with potassium carbonate. It was then thoroughly extracted with ether, ethereal layer dried over $MgSO_4$, solvent evaporated, and the residue distilled in vacuum using a fractionating Claisen. The alcohols were redistilled before polarometric measurements. The distillate in each case was examined by vapour phase

chromatography and found to contain only one peak. The recovery of the two carbinols described in this paper was approximately 50%. The rotations were measured in 1dm. tube using sodium light. All experiments were duplicated. In one of the experiments, methylphenylcarbinol was converted into acid phthalate; it had $[\alpha]_D^{20}$ -6.98, corresponding to 19% optical purity approximately.

The physical characteristics and yields of recovery of some of the alcohols are given below:

Ethylmethylcarbinol, b.p. 98-100°; n_D^{20} 1.3927; yield, 20-25%.

Isopropylmethylcarbinol, b.p. 110-112°, n_D^{20} 1.4052; yield, 20-28%.

Isobutylmethylcarbinol, b.p. 135-137°; n_D^{20} 1.4087; yield, 30-33%.

t-Butylmethylcarbinol, b.p. 120-122°; n_D^{20} 1.4137; yield, 12-15%

Phenylmethylcarbinol, b.p. 83-85°/12mm.; n_D^{20} 1.5252; yield 50%.

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